

Impact of Oil and Gas Revenue on Economic Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of oil and gas revenue on the GDP of Nigeria from 1980 to 2023. Data were obtained from secondary sources, notably the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin. The study adopted the ordinary least square regression technique. The study used per capita income (CPY) as the dependent variable, which is used to proxy the level of activities that reflect national development, and oil and gas revenue as the independent variable, which is used to proxy the level of contribution to the economy. The period covered in this study is 1980–2023. The model used in this study includes per capita income as a dependent variable and independent variables such as non-oil revenue, oil price volatility, and oil revenue. The findings of the study reveal that oil and gas revenue generated by the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) has a positive and significant influence on per capita income vis-à-vis national development. This means that oil revenue has a positive impact on the economy; that is, a percent rise in oil revenue will lead to a small rise in per capita income (CPY). Furthermore, it is observed that there is a straight relationship between non-oil revenue and per capita income. Meaning, every one percent rise in non-oil revenue will ensure an increase in the per capita income of Nigerians. The study also revealed that oil price volatility has a negative influence on per capita income in Nigeria. From the results above, it is observed that Nigeria, as a major oil exporter, has felt a significant impact of recent events on its economy. Market growth expectations for 2023 have fall significantly, precipitated by a declining oil price and an increase in political instability, most recently seen in a cash crunch from the cashless policy of the CBN and the preparation for elections in Nigeria. The fluctuation in the price of oil has conventionally placed significant pressure on the local currency's (Naira) exchange rate. It is recommended, among others, that the Nigerian government utilise revenue derived from the sale of petroleum and gas-related products to cater for the environs

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affected by the unnecessary and deliberate flaring. Also, the Nigerian government should utilise the revenue generated to enhance the development and revival of local refineries in the country. This they should do by making the refineries operate, if not at 100 percent capacity utilisation, at least at a percentage close to it; the government should enhance revenue generated from crude oil proceeds and diversify it to other sectors of the Nigerian economy; Pump prices in Nigeria have risen to about N700 per litre, depending on your location. The government should use the excess revenue from crude oil to keep pump-head prices at an affordable price. Government ministries should encourage people to return to agriculture by providing technical input and financial support. This will require an overhaul of the land tenure system to facilitate easy access, and the government should encourage both the public and private sectors to invest more. This could be done by strengthening the manufacturing sector through tax incentives and infrastructure development through a public-private sector partnership.

Keywords: Oil Revenue, Gas Revenue, Oil Price Volatility, Economic Development

1.0 Introduction

Oil and gas are major sources of energy in Nigeria and the world at large. Over time, the resources have been the mainstay of the Nigerian economy and play a vital role in shaping the economic and political destiny of the country. Although Nigeria's oil industry was founded at the beginning of the century, it was not until the end of the Nigerian civil war that the oil industry began to play a prominent role in the economic life of the country (Odularu, 2008). Rewane (2007) stated that 1973–1985 was the period of Nigeria's third and fourth national development plans, which were launched against a background of abundant financial resources following sharp increases in both the price of crude oil and Nigeria's level of production. From late 1973 to mid-1974, oil revenues increased through greater public ownership and higher taxes and royalties." Gelb (1988). Subsequent eras have witnessed vast revenue from the oil and gas industry in Nigeria. However, according to Anyanwa (1997), petroleum has transformed poor nations into rich ones, deserts into watersheds, and bankrupt nations into creditors. Specifically, with respect to Nigeria, there is no gainsaying that the oil sector has undergone tremendous transformation over the years. The excess revenue made from

the oil sector can be invested into variable sectors in order to diversify the economy and also increase the total gross domestic product (GDP) of the economy. Over the past decades, the oil industry has made a variety of contributions to the Nigerian economy. These have included the creation of employment opportunities, local expenditure on goods and services, contributions to government revenues and to foreign exchange reserves, and the supply of energy to industry and commerce. But the main question remains: has the impact of the oil revenue generated over the decades been equally significant on the Nigerian economy in terms of increasing the total GDP, the total per capita income, and the overall standard of living of the Nigerian populace?

According to the CIA (2012), Nigeria is ranked the 13th largest oil-producing country in the world as of 2013, with a total of 2.5 million bbl/day and 3.5 million bbl/day in 2021. However, almost fifty years after the oil was discovered at Oloibiri in south-eastern Nigeria, the evident in economic and social infrastructural development in the country does not reflect the revenue derived from the petroleum industry. This is clearly evident in the absence of basic infrastructural facilities in the form of health care, educational services, development projects, and basic amenities like electricity and water, among others, that should befit the world's 13th largest oil-producing country. The absence of these basic infrastructural faculties is due to the fact that revenue derived from oil exports has been largely mismanaged by the successive governments in power. Thus, one of the biggest challenges for Nigeria, an oil-producing country, is how to use its oil revenue strategically to promote sustainable national development. It has become apparent that the revenue from oil and gas has not been properly allocated or, better still used adequately to the benefit of the country (NEITI, 2009). Although large proceeds are obtained from the domestic sales and export of petroleum products, its effect on growth requires evaluating the relative impacts of crude oil on the economy. In light of the problem of the study, this study stands to analyse the impact of oil and gas revenue generated from the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) on national development in Nigeria.

1.2 Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of oil and gas revenue on the GDP of Nigeria.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Oil revenue in this study refers to the income earned from the sales of crude oil. Oil and gas abstraction play a leading role as a basis for export earnings and, to a lesser extent, employment in many developing countries. But the most significant advantage for a nation from the development of the oil and gas sector is likely to be its fiscal role in creating taxes and other revenue for the government. To ensure that the state, as a resource owner, obtains a suitable share of the economic rent created from the abstraction of oil and gas, the fiscal regime must be appropriately planned.

The government, as the owner of the resource, has an appreciated asset in the country. These assets—crude oil and natural gas deposits—can only be exploited once. In order to convert this asset into financial resources, the government must finance capital to ensure it gets the highest likely value for its resources. It should be noted that the government can gather revenue from the oil and gas sector through a variety of tax and nontax tools in the Nigerian economy. Most nations collect the government share of economic rent mostly through production-based or profit-based tools. In some nations, the government partakes more directly in projects by taking an equity interest. Policymakers will also have to decide on the treatment of indirect taxes such as VAT and customs duties that will help the Nigerian economy grow.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Economic growth, according to Henderson and Poole, is seen as the increase in output and other measures of material progress over a certain period. It is also said to be either growth in national output as measured by GDP or GNP (which measures economic power) or growth in the national average standard of living as measured by the GNP per capita (which measures the well-being of citizens). Economic growth focuses on the expansion of productive capacity over time. The expansion of productive capacity requires an increase in natural resources, human resources, capital, and technology. Thus, economic growth is due to growth in inputs such as labour, capital, and technological improvement. Economic growth, generally, can be described as a positive change in the level of production of goods and services by a country over a certain period of time. In other words, economic growth is the increase in the value of goods and services produced by an economy. It can also be referred to as the increase in the gross domestic product. It is a relatively straight-forward measure of output and gives an idea

of how well off a country is compared with competitors and past performance. It is a beacon that helps policymakers steer the economy towards key economic objectives. Economic growth is referred to as a measure of the wellbeing of a state, usually in real terms.

2.1.1 Mainstream Theory

Their argument was that countries should produce and export according to their comparative advantages. Looking at the comparative advantage theory, it suggests that a nation will gain more economic benefit relative to other nations if they produce a commodity that they have in abundance at a lower cost. In their argument, they said nations trading with them will benefit more if they accept the cost advantage of the trading nation and concentrate on producing those goods which they have an advantage. This theory is the main focus of mainstream economists. They believe in free trade, specialisation, and the international division of labour. They argue that this is the reason why some nations of the world specialise in the production of industrial commodities and others on primary commodities.

The theory argues that it benefits countries to produce and export commodities they can use their abundant productive factors effectively. The theory assumes that two countries, two goods, and two factors are involved, and it also assumes that these countries have the same technologies and tastes and free trade in goods but different factor endowments. The theory argues that as long as two nations of the world have different factor endowments, trade will be beneficial to them. In their argument, they opined that differences in factor endowments lead to specialisation, which will enable them to export goods in which they have a comparative advantage. Heckscher and Ohlin therefore argue that countries with abundance of capital would export capital-intensive products and import labour-intensive ones, while those with abundance of labour would export labour-intensive products and import capital-intensive ones. According to this theory, countries that have oil should produce it using low-cost technology and export same to countries that do not have oil.

2.1.2 New Institutional Economics Theory

New institutional economics (NIE) is a subgroup of mainstream economics that suggests that mainstream economists' assumptions of perfect information, no

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transaction costs, perfect competition, and unbounded rationality are not always valid. NIE instead studies the written and unwritten rules and laws that govern society and government and are meant to control society and reduce uncertainty. They assume individuals do not have perfect information and, due to their limited mental capacity, create formal and informal institutions to reduce the risk of uncertainty and transaction costs. Individuals develop systems of organisation to motivate agents. Therefore, the performance of the economy is dependent on both formal and informal institutions. While mainstream economics focuses on prices and outcomes, NIE considers the effects of institutions. According to NIE, transaction costs are dependent on the institutional setting; therefore, the political institutions are influential in rules, laws, and contracts. However, both NIE and mainstream accept the assumptions of competition and scarcity. NIE attempts to answer the question surrounding the inability of countries to foster sustainable growth and looks to the role of institutions as the answer. According to the NIE, countries with high transaction costs have less trade, specialisation, investment, and productivity. In the following section, we look at NIE literature, which aims to explain the underdevelopment of resource-abundant countries, which, according to mainstream economists, are ideally supposed to grow faster than resource-poor countries. However, this has not been the case in NIE.

2.1.3 Resource Endowment Theory of Growth:

The main person behind this theory was Adam Smith in his absolute cost advantage theory, as modelled by David Ricardo in his comparative cost advantage theory. They argued in their theory that countries should specialise in producing and exporting according to their comparative advantage. The theory of comparative advantage suggests that a nation gains more economic profit relative to other nations by producing using a less-cost technology in the production process. They argued that a nation can gain more when producing commodities that the country has in abundance or can easily produce. Other nations, according to the theory, will therefore benefit from trade only if they accept the cost advantage of the trading nation and focus on producing a commodity in which they have an advantage. Therefore, when talking about resource endowment, it guides resource endowment economists' beliefs in free trade, specialisation, and the international division of labour. This was the reason why some

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countries prefer to produce agricultural and mineral products while others prefer to produce industrial products, according to the theory. The doctrine of comparative advantage, according to the Heckscher-Ohlin (HO) theory, states that nations produce and export commodities that require the use of its abundant productive factors intensely. The assumption of this theory is based on two goods and two factors; it also assumes that both countries have identical technologies, identical tastes, free trade in goods, and different factor endowments. This theory was based on the proposition that nations with an abundance of capital would export capital-intensive goods and import labour-intensive goods, while nations with an abundance of labour would export labour-intensive goods and import capital-intensive goods.

2.2 Literature Review

Ekpo (2021) used data from Asia to test the validity of the HO model. Singapore, which is a capital-abundant country, is compared with Malaysia, a relatively labour-abundant country with little capital. Clarke et al.'s aim was to find out if the exports of both countries are what one would expect based on the HO theory (Clarke et al. 2020). They hypothesize that the capital-abundant country will export more capital goods and the labour-intensive country will export more labour-intensive goods (Clarke et al. 2020). Data was collected from the United Nations regarding traded commodities between the two countries in 2007 (Clarke et al. 2020). When comparing the data between the two countries, they find that Singapore's exports are comparatively capital intensive to Malaysia's exports, which are relatively labour intensive. However, when looking at the ratios, they found that capital-intensive exports were 32 percent of all Singapore's exports, which is relatively low by HO theory standards. However, Clarke et al. still concluded that the Singapore-Malaysia trade in 1997 behaved according to the theory of comparative advantage, and therefore they would both experience growth.

According to Bawa and Mohammed (2021) study, they used the ordinary least squares regression method to investigate the relationship that exists between the crude oil sector and Nigerian economic performance and concluded that oil has contributed to the improvement of the country. However, in the study, they recommended that the government should implement policies that encourage private businesses to participate actively in the oil sector. This study, as of that time, covered a time period of 1970 to 2005. The weakness of this work is that it has become obsolete.

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Salehi and Mohaddes (2020) had, through their study, developed a growth model in the long run. In the study, they indicated how oil revenue will impact the economy in the long run. The study revealed that the log of oil exports from 1976 to 2006 entered the long run output equation with a coefficient equal to the share of capital. They opined that the Iranian economy adjusts more quickly to shocks in foreign output and oil exports, which could be partly due to the relatively underdeveloped nature of Iran's financial markets. Though the study investigated Iranian's economy, it is vital that if Nigeria wants to develop, they should learn lesson from Iran. This will strengthen the Nigerian economy.

Abubakar A. (2015), in historical research where he collected secondary data from the use of statistical records maintained by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), examined the impact of the global fall in oil prices on the Nigerian crude oil revenue and prices. The data were analysed using a T-test to determine whether there is any significant difference existing between oil revenue generated by Nigeria prior to the fall, during the fall, and after the fall of crude oil prices in the global market. The result showed that the global fall in oil prices has a significant impact on crude oil revenue and prices in Nigeria.

Ogbonna and Appah (2012), in their study, investigated the impact of petroleum revenue on the economy of Nigeria for the period 1970–2012. In the study, primary and secondary data were used. The primary data was generated from a questionnaire administered to 150 oil and gas and non-oil and gas workers in Rivers and Bayelsa states, respectively. The secondary data was collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The collected data were analysed using Ordinary Least Square Regression (OLS), Pearson product correlation coefficient, and descriptive statistics. In the results, it was discovered that petroleum revenue affects the gross domestic product and per capita income of Nigeria positively. Also in the study, it was discovered that the relationship between petroleum revenue and inflation rate was negative. In conclusion, the research revealed that the revenue generated from petroleum exploration in Nigeria has contributed positively to the gross domestic product and per capita income. This means that if the revenue is properly managed, it will help Nigeria to develop more.

Attamah (2021), in his study on the impact of oil wealth on the economic growth of a monocultural economy in Nigeria from 1980 to 2012, used multiple regression analysis with the application of the OLS econometric technique to carry out the study.

The study revealed that the manufacturing sector and interest rate contributed negatively to economic growth, while the agricultural and oil sectors contributed positively to economic growth. In the study, he compared the contribution of agricultural and oil sectors to the Nigerian economy. The result showed that agricultural sector contributed more to GDP than the oil sector.

A study carried out by Anyanwu (2000) showed that dependence on oil revenue has directly and indirectly created problems for fiscal sustainability and economic management in Nigeria. It is obvious that the price of oil is exogenously determined. This situation affects revenue. The annual budget for Nigeria is a function of the price of crude oil given the quantity of oil production, determined by the OPEC quota for the country. According to his study, during the oil boom in Nigeria, agricultural production was neglected. Primary commodities suffer from the problem of produce preservation, leading to rapid deterioration and quality loss. This is one of the reasons for the dominance of the oil sector.

Azaiki and Shagary, H. (2020) used the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression method to investigate the impact of oil and gas on the economy in Nigeria. They found out that there was misappropriation of oil proceeds from the crude oil sales. This, according to them, has affected the development of other sectors of the economy negatively. This situation has forced the oil sector to shoulder over 80% of the economic burdens of the country. They argued that the economy of Nigeria has for a very long period been a mono-dependent economy; this is attributed to the poor administrative technique of redistributing the revenue from oil wealth to ensure balanced growth. This is a result of the poor and inefficient performance of the supervisory institutions in the country. Lack of commitment by past administrations in Nigeria to develop other sectors has affected the human and infrastructural development of the country.

3. Methodology

The method used in this study is the ordinary least square method. This method is used to enable the researchers to observe the effect of oil and gas revenue on the economic development of Nigeria. The OLS method is chosen for this work because it is the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE). In this study, GDP is expected to be the dependent variable, which is used to proxy the level of activities that reflect national development, while oil and gas revenue is proxied as the independent variable, which is used to proxy

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the level of contribution to the economy. The period covered in this study is 1980–2023. The data for this study was obtained mainly from secondary sources, particularly time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The model used in this study is of this form:

$$PCY=f(ORV, OPV, NRV) \dots\dots\dots i$$

This model can be rewritten as follows:

$$LPCY = a_0 + a_1 LORV + a_2 LOPV + a_3 LNRV + \mu \dots\dots\dots ii$$

Where:

- LPCY = Log of Per Capita Income
- LORV = Log of Oil Revenue
- LOPV = Log of Oil Price Volatility
- LNRV = Log of Non-Oil Revenue

4. Presentation and Interpretation of Result

Considering the results of the appraised model outlined in the methodology above, we present it in this section, having compared the results of this study with those of other studies for advanced economies and developing exporting countries. It is vital to say that, given the significant doubts involved in specifying and estimating this class of model, mostly in the background of advanced economy, the paper broadly engaged in a wide plan search, and in particularly drop numerous variables that attest to have the incorrect signs. This should be noted when groping the reported standard errors. The empirical results gotten from the multiple regression, using the ordinary least squares (OLS) techniques, are presented thus:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	PCY	NRV	OPV	ORV
Mean	1776.781	920.0058	42.2058	2309.868
Median	1548.300	269.6250	22.0000	977.6350
Maximum	3224.711	3275.030	145.0000	8878.970
Minimum	1324.300	2.9800	0.1500	7.250000
Std. Dev.	514.4605	1172.668	47.37152	2674.280
Observations	43	43	43	43

Source: Computed using E-view 9, 2023

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Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics result of the dependent and independent variables. A total of 43 observations were recorded. The table shows the mean, median, and standard deviation with the minimum and maximum range of the dependent and independent variables. The per capita income (PCY), which is a dependent variable, has an average of 1776.781bn and a median of 1548.300bn with a minimum of 1324.300bn; and a maximum of 3224.711bn with a standard deviation of 514.4605bn representing 100%, showing that there is much variation among the PCY of the sampled companies. The non-oil revenue (NRV), which is an independent variable, has an average of 920.0058bn and a median of 269.6250bn with a minimum of 2.980000bn and a maximum of 3275.030bn with a standard deviation of 1172.668bn representing 100%, showing that there is much variation among the NRV of the sampled companies. The oil price volatility (OPV), which is an independent variable, has an average of 42.20579bn and a median of 22.00000bn, with a minimum of 0.150000bn and a maximum of 145.0000bn with a standard deviation of 47.37152bn representing 100%, showing that there is much variation among the OPV of the sampled companies. The oil revenue (ORV), which is an independent variable, has an average of 2309.868bn and a median of 977.6350bn, with a minimum of 7.250000bn and a maximum of 8878.970bn, with a standard deviation of 2674.280bn representing 100%, showing that there is much variation among the ORV of the sampled companies.

4.1 Presentation of Result

Table 4.2: Regression Result

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	18.4800	2.1680	0.0372
NRV	0.1669	10.1414	0.0000
OPV	-1.2132	-3.2987	0.0023
ORV	0.0121	3.2406	0.0027
R-squared	0.8581		
Adjusted R squared	- 0.8544		
F-statistic	59.03201		
Durbin-Watson stat		0.216723	

Source: Author's Computation 2023

The result from the table above reveals that non-oil revenue has positive value of 0.1669. This is not consistent with the a priori expectation. The result shows that the coefficient of this variable is statistically significant at 0.05 significant levels. The implication of this is that a percent rise in average will lead to 16.5% rise in per capita income of Nigerians. Furthermore, it is observed that the coefficient of oil price volatility has a negative value of -1.2132. Having been in consistent with the a priori expectation, it means that there is straight relationship between oil price volatility and per capita income. The result also explains that for every one percent variation in oil price will ensure 12.13 percent decrease in per capita income of Nigerians. The study also revealed that oil revenue has a positive coefficient of 0.0121. The result show that the value of the intercept which is 18.4800 of per capita income of Nigerians will enhance 18.4800 rise in the per capita income of people in the country. The result also revealed that the R-square of the regression is 0.8581. The overall goodness of the model as shown by the adjusted coefficient of determination is 0.8581. This means that about 85 percent of the variation experienced in the per capita income of Nigerians is explained by the independent variables included in the model. Further investigation shows that F-statistic, which measures the joint statistical influence of the explanatory variables in explaining the dependent variable, was found to be statistically significant at 0.05 percent level. The value of the F-statistic is 59.03201 and this shows that the explanatory variables are important determinants of per capita income in Nigerian economy. Considering the Durbin Watson statistic, the value shows 0.216723 which means that there is autocorrelation among the explanatory variables in the model.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

From the results above, it is observed that Nigeria, as a major oil exporter, has felt a significant negative impact of recent events on its economy. Market growth expectations for 2021 have fallen significantly, precipitated by a declining oil price and an increase in political instability, most recently seen in a cash crunch from the cashless policy of the CBN and the preparation for elections in Nigeria. The oil sector has changed the structure of the Nigerian economy since production began in the 1960s. It can be seen that today oil and gas are the main sources of export earnings for both individuals and governments. In 2021, Nigerian oil accounted for 90% of Nigeria's export revenues, around 70% of the government's income, and nearly 11% of the country's GDP. Worthy

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of note is that with high dependency on oil, the Nigerian economy does not diversify well, and its taxing system favours mostly the rich at the expense of the poor, and its tax base is low as compared to other countries at a parallel level of development. The drastic drop in oil prices recently has negatively affected the economy, and it adds to the already existing problem of production failures, spillages, high bunkering, and theft rates in the Niger Delta region of the country. These scenarios have put pressure on the quantity of production in the country.

A fall in the price of oil has conventionally placed significant pressure on the local currency's (Naira) exchange rate band. The Central Bank of Nigeria has responded to the recent oil price decline by drawing down on reserves and accepting greater exchange rate flexibility. The institution has also decided to change the old naira notes to new ones. This policy has greatly affected the Nigerian economy.

Let it be noted that there is no doubt that the upstream sector of the oil industry in Nigeria has developed above average, and that trend has attracted large foreign capital inflows. However, the return on the oil and gas investment has been good. It should be noted that the revenue generated from these sub-sectors should have provided the required capital that can aid other sectors of the Nigerian economy, particularly those that have the highest socio-economic impact. Based on the above scenarios, we make the following policy recommendations:

1. Government should strengthen the refineries for them to operate if not at 100 percent capacity utilization, at least at a percentage close to it;
2. Revenue generated from crude oil proceeds should be diversified to other sectors of the Nigerian economy;
3. Government should use the excess revenue from crude oil to keep pump-head prices at affordable price;
4. Government ministries should ensure people are encouraged to return to agriculture by providing technical inputs and financial support. This will require an overhaul of the land tenure system to facilitate easy access; and
5. Government should encourage both the private and public sectors to invest more and this could be done by strengthening the manufacturing sector through tax incentives and infrastructure development by way of public-private sector partnership.

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